

Determination of fluoride: Aliquots of iron(III) (0.0025 M; 4 ml), 2-HANO (0.025 M; 4 ml) and sulphuric acid (0.05 M; 10 ml) were mixed and shaken well. Aliquots of fluoride (1–20 μg) were then added to the complex and the solution was made upto 25 ml mark with distilled water. After 15 min the absorbance of the solutions was measured at 600 nm against the reagent blank.

We reported⁷ earlier that 1-HANO formed a greenish violet 1:1 complex with iron(III) in the pH range 2.0–4.0. We now report the use of this complex as well for the determination of fluoride.

Aliquots of iron(III) (0.0025 M; 2 ml), 1-HANO (0.025 M; 2 ml) and sulphuric acid (0.05 M; 10 ml) were mixed and shaken well. Aliquots of fluoride (1–20 μg) were then added to the complex and the contents made up to the 25 ml with 95% ethanol (v/v). The absorbance of the solutions was measured at 640 nm after 15 min against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The basis of the estimation of iron(III) is the formation of intense greenish violet coloured complex by 2-HANO with iron(III). The results reveal that in the presence of five-fold excess of the reagent the iron(III)-2-HANO complex obeyed Beer's law in the range 1–18 μg of iron(III) in 25 ml.

Studies made using Job's mole-ratio, slope-ratio and Ausmus methods indicate that 2-HANO forms a 1:2 (metal-ligand) complex with iron(III). The Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorptivity were found to be 0.046 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and $4.0 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. Identification limit and dilution limit were found to be 0.46 μg and $1:14.9 \times 10^3$ respectively. The stability constant of the complex determined by Ausmus method was found to be 6.25×10^8 . Diverse ions such as Fe^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ag^{+} , Be^{2+} , La^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , chloride, bromide, iodide, carbonate, sulphite, sulphate, acetate do not interfere even when present in ten-fold excess to iron(III). More than 0.5 ppm of V^{5+} , Ti^{4+} and Cu^{2+} interfere under the experimental conditions. Fluoride and phosphate seriously interfere at all levels.

Fluoride was estimated based on the principle that it reacts with iron(III) to form a complex which is stronger than the iron(III) complex with the reagent. A plot of ΔA vs concentration of fluoride, indicates that amounts of fluoride in the range 1–9 μg in 25 ml could be determined by using iron(III)-2-HANO complex and 2–9 μg in 25 ml could be determined using iron(III)-1-HANO complex.

The accuracy is comparable to that of the standard procedure using SPADNS reagent⁸ for

the determination of fluoride. The standard deviation is 0.00326 and 0.00554 for 1-HANO and 2-HANO systems respectively. Moreover, the reagent could be easily prepared.

The metals like Th^{IV} , Zr^{III} , Be^{II} , B^{III} , V^{V} , Cu^{II} , Ti^{IV} , Sr^{II} and Ce^{II} seriously interfere in both the methods for the estimation of fluoride.

2-HANO reacts with iron(III) only in acidic pH, the reaction being unaffected by the presence of iron(II). Thus the reagent is useful to determine iron(III) in the presence of iron(II) for which very few reagents qualify.

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Extraction Photo metric Determination of Microgram Amounts of Cobalt with Thiocyanate and Cetyltrimethylammonium Bromide

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THE thiocyanate complex of cobalt, which is not extractable into chloroform, readily forms extractable ion-pair with the quaternary ammonium ion derived from cetyltrimethylammonium bromide. Measurement of absorbance of this extract forms the basis of the present method for the estimation of μg amounts of cobalt.

Experimental

Cobalt solution was prepared from $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and standardised. Solutions of 0.2 M

ammonium thiocyanate and 0.1 M cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) was prepared in distilled water. Acetate buffer was used for adjustment of pH of the aqueous solution. Acidity was measured with an ECL 5651 digital pH meter.

A Shimadzu PR-1 spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurement.

Procedure: To an aliquot of the cobalt(II) solution containing upto 300 μg of cobalt, ammonium thiocyanate (2 ml) and CTAB solutions (0.4 ml) were added. The total volume of the aqueous phase was made upto 10 ml with acetate buffer and distilled water so that pH of the solution was maintained at 3.5 ± 0.5 . The resulting mixture was then shaken (30 s) with chloroform (10 ml). The separated blue organic layer was poured over anhydrous sodium sulphate to remove any retained water droplets. The absorbance of the chloroform extract was then measured at 625 nm against the reagent blank and the amount of cobalt estimated. To test the interference, foreign ions were added to the aqueous solution before addition of the reagents.

Results and Discussion

The reaction between cobalt(II), thiocyanate and CTAB was instantaneous. 1 ml of ammonium thiocyanate along with 0.2 ml of CTAB was sufficient to extract 135 μg of cobalt in a single operation. Higher concentrations of the reagent, however, did not bring about any significant change in the maximum value of absorbance.

A steady and maximum absorbance was obtained when the extractions were carried out throughout the entire range, i.e. from 4 M HCl medium to pH 8.0. In each case the remaining aqueous phase, after a single extraction, was void of cobalt as tested by an independent method. At 0.1 M sodium hydroxide medium, cobalt(II) showed no colour reaction with the reagents.

The $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{-SCN-CTAB}$ complex in chloroform exhibited absorption maxima at 625 nm with a shoulder around 585 nm. The reagent blank does not absorb in the aforesaid wavelength region. The pattern of the absorption spectrum of the complex, extracted throughout the entire range (4 M HCl medium to pH 8.0) remained unchanged. This indicates the existence of a single variety of the complex species in the system. The absorbance of the chloroform extract remained virtually constant for at least 96 h.

The absorbance of the blue complex in chloroform showed a linear response upto 3 ppm of cobalt. The molar absorptivity of the complex, based on cobalt content, was evaluated to be $1.92 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with the corresponding Sandell's sensitivity of $0.031 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ at 625 nm.

Interference: In order to study the effects of diverse ions on the extraction behaviour, cobalt was extracted and determined according to the

recommended procedure in presence of the respective foreign ions. Extraction pH was set at 3.5 with acetate buffer, unless otherwise mentioned. An ion was considered to interfere if the recovery of cobalt differed by more than $\pm 3\%$ from the actual amount taken. Cobalt(II) (135 μg) could be determined without interference in presence of 50–60 fold excess of Be^{II} , Tl^{I} , Al^{III} , Th^{IV} , U^{VI} , Pt^{IV} , Rh^{III} , La^{III} , Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Sr^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cr^{III} , Bi^{III} , Pb^{II} , V^{V} , Ni^{II} , Ag^{I} , Zr^{IV} , Mg^{II} , Ce^{III} , Sn^{II} . The system tolerated 20–5 fold excess of Mo^{IV} and Fe^{III} (more than 50-fold excess in presence of ammonium hydrogenfluoride), and 5–10 fold excess of Pd^{II} . A 30-fold excess of Cd^{II} did not interfere if the extraction be carried out from 3 M HCl medium. In presence of Cu^{II} , the chloroform extract became hazy and absorption of the organic layer could not be measured, and this interference could not be removed. Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} must be absent as Co^{II} showed no colour reaction in their presence.

Among the anions tested, a 100-fold excess of thiosulphate, iodide, fluoride, phosphate, acetate, phthalate, tartrate, ascorbate, sulphate, and a 30-fold excess of citrate and oxalate did not have any effect. Extraction should be carried out from 3 M HCl medium to avoid the interference due to EDTA.

The proposed method was tested by analysing solutions containing a known amount of cobalt. The average of six determinations of 135 μg Co was found to be 133 μg with the relative mean deviation of $\pm 1.3\%$.

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Extraction of Lead with a Liquid Anion Exchanger and its Application in Rat Tissue Samples

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IN the present paper we describe a method for selective quantitative extraction of trace quantities of lead as its complex with nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) using the liquid anion-exchanger, Aliquat 336 in cyclohexane and its subsequent determination by flame AAS. The method has been successfully applied to determine lead content in kidney and liver tissues of *Rattus norvegicus*.